

DEAD LANGUAGES AND WORDS OUT OF USE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7205314>

Annotation: Disappearance of languages and its causes. Other languages and their history. Importance of languages in the world.

Keywords: language, nation, people, loss, dead language, Latin language

Why does language die? The answers to this question vary. According to calculations based on various sources, it is recognized that there are 3,000 to 7,000 languages in the world today. Different factors caused the development or death of languages in each period. Colonialism until the 20th century, urbanization in the 20th century, and globalization in the 21st century caused the death of languages. The number of languages dying in the last decade is more than in the last century. The death of these languages is mainly due to the fact that people did not use them, they were not given the status of a state language. Giving the language the status of a state language relieves it to a certain extent from the risk of extinction. Languages are like people, they live side by side, influence each other, change and develop. The fact that the world is becoming a single information space as a result of the acceleration of development has a great impact on the fate of languages. For example, in the last millennium, 500 of the world's languages became dead languages, and in the last century, 1,000 languages sank into the depths of history. Whichever language is more important, more convenient, as a result of which more attention is paid to that language on a world scale, minor languages remain unimportant, secondary or completely unnecessary. Some languages have disappeared due to invasion, colonization, and historical changes. For example, Sumerian, Bulgarian, Latin, Prussian, Visigoth, Ostrogoth, Orkhon, Coptic, ancient Persian, Sanskrit, Pali and several other languages are considered dead languages. Some dead languages are still used even after thousands of years have passed. For example, Egyptian Christians are from the Coptic language, representatives of the Catholic Church are from the Latin language. A child learns a living language, he receives it from his parents. A dead language is called so because it does not pass from generation to generation. At present, the history of the past has been studied and many families of dead languages related to each other have been identified. For example, the "Ved" language, which belongs to the Indo-European language family, is the language of the "Ved", which is considered the ancient sacred book of the Indians; "Sanskrit" language is the classical literary language of the ancient Indians from the 3rd century BC to the 7th century AD; "Pali" language - the

language of literary and religious worship in the Middle Ages; Dead languages belonging to the group of Iranian languages: "Old Persian" language - the language of the Achaemenids in the VI-IV centuries BC; The "Pahlavi" language is based on the Pahlavi script. In addition, such as the "Parthian" language, the "Sogdian" language, the "Khorazm" language, the "Scythian" language, the "Bactrian" language and the "Saklar" language. Dead languages belonging to the group of Slavic languages: "Old Slavic" language - common literary language of the Slavs in the Middle Ages; The "Czech" language is based on the Latin alphabet, the oldest written monuments date back to the 13th century. In addition, languages such as Slovak, Kashubian, Lujitsa, Polish, and Pomor are considered dead languages. Many other languages have become dead languages. All languages are classified according to survival rate as follows: -Safe languages -Careful languages - Endangered languages -Endangered languages - Dying languages. The Uzbek language is one of the most popular languages today. Despite the fact that the Uzbek language has its own script, the status of a state language, and has more than 30 million speakers, it is a bitter truth that it should be noted that the fact that it is not promoted as an Internet language is its loss. It shows that it is not completely safe from danger, and it remains in the list of foreign languages. Today's most secure languages are: English, Chinese, Japanese, Arabic, Spanish, and French. How do languages survive? The answer to this question is related to the Internet. Any language that is not the language of the Internet is in danger of death. Ancient Egyptians and Khorezms, Greeks and Indians, Chinese and Persians put forward different scientific hypotheses about the origin and stages of evolution of language. There are words that, even though they have become dead words, still have an alternative option. For example, the word "Ghassal" in dialects is Arabic, its meaning "dead washer" is now obsolete, instead of it the meaning "unpleasant" is used. Also, the meaning of the word "magzhava" meaning "dirty water" is out of use, the word "kullab" means "rod" and the word "myyt" means dead. 'nosi was used in the old sense of "coffin". In addition, the meaning of the word "Khalpa" is hidden from a literate student, the meaning of the word "battal" is "kaysar", "tentak", "oxur" is "stable". is also obsolete - out of circulation. Historical words - something that does not exist now - are names of phenomena that have completely fallen out of use, where the word becomes obsolete with the concept it represents. For example, ten head, thousand head, halfa, maid, doorman. Archaic words - something that does not exist now - are the names of phenomena that have completely fallen out of use. In this case, the word becomes obsolete, but the concept does not become obsolete, it remains to be expressed by

another word. For example, rayon (district), redaktor (editor), ulus (nation), bitik (writing). In short, the preservation of the Uzbek language, in general, the preservation of the languages of the world, depends not only on the Internet, but on the intellectuals, the youth, and the authorities. Our mother tongue will never die if we all come together and roll up our sleeves to fulfill the tasks and succeed.

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